

Implementation of Good Governance in the Defense Sector To Improve the Quality of Human Capital of Indonesia Government

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ABSTRACT: *The Republic of Indonesia is currently facing various challenges that require serious attention. Good governance is part of developing a new paradigm, offering colorful nuances to fill the needs of the reform era, especially after the multifaceted crisis. Such situations and situations require future national leadership. The widening gap in the process of political communication that occurs in Indonesia between the government and the people, the people, and political parties representing voters. This is a problem of complex phenomena to understand in the logic of the general public. Good and Clean Governance have definitions of all related things with action or direct Act behavior, control, or affect public affairs for realizing values in life every day. In Indonesia, good governance could be considered good, clean, and authoritative. In line with system accountability implemented by the President Republic of Indonesia to the whole institution national, including TNI, the development of a career in the TNI environment must be based on the related principles of good governance accountability. To reach Thing above and implement the main mission military is precise, efficient, effective, and quality. Of course, need existence professional components, responsible answers, and fairness and sincerity. Competent in every field. Pamen TNI must depend on qualified skills and competencies for operating tasks. The conclusion is good governance is how to serve the public with the best to society. If the service is efficient, meaning reverse comparison between input and output achieved with minimal input, then level efficiency becomes better.*

KEYWORDS – Defense, Good Government, Human Capital

I. INTRODUCTION

In the world and national development dynamics, the Republic of Indonesia is currently facing various challenges that require serious attention. Good governance is part of developing a new paradigm, offering colorful nuances to fill the needs of the reform era, especially after the multifaceted crisis. Such situations and situations require future national leadership, which is expected to be able to answer the challenges of the Indonesian state in the future. The evolution of national affairs today consists of three phenomena, increasingly complex problems (multidimensional) and rapid changes (rules, policies, actions, and reactions of society), characterized by relative uncertainty.

The widening gap in the process of political communication that occurs in Indonesia between the government and the people, the people, and political parties representing voters. This is a problem of complex phenomena to understand in the logic of the general public.

Solving the problems above requires the commitment of various stakeholders interested in society, not only the government and politicians, who must contribute to building good governance. For this reason, all parties need to understand the complex understanding of good governance as part of efforts to help create good governance. Because of Thing's interest, this article attempts to explain the concepts, principles, and practices of good management for the benefit of the state. In this case, the author describes how the implementation of good governance, especially in the defense sector, can be applied in Indonesia.

Author writing article scientific with use method study qualitative and technical data collection in the form of Studies Literature and Library Research. Studies literature obtained from various types of essays in range the time 2010 to 2022 is good already reputable or not reputation and assessment appropriate literature books with theory primarily related with the implementation of good governance in the sector defense to use face progress globalization, apart from that references obtained from several documents, news, reports yearly and others. Analyzed journals from several journals, and all articles cited scientific were sourced from Publish, Perish, and Google Scholar.

II. DISCUSSION 1. Understanding Good Governance

Good and Clean Governance have definitions of all related things with action or direct Act behavior, control, or affect public affairs for realizing values in life every day. In Indonesia, good governance could be considered good, clean, and authoritative. It means good that is relevant state government with source social, cultural, political, and economy set under-exercised power society. At the same time, a clean government is an effective, efficient, transparent, honest, and responsible government answer.

Good and Clean Governance could come true maximum if elements of the state and society civil (of n which there is sector private) each other related. Condition or provisions so that the government can walk with a good, that is can move by synergistic, no each other clash or opposite and get Support from people, development held by effective and efficient in Thing cost and time. According to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), one of the UN agencies, governance has three models, namely:

- a. Economic Governance, includes the process of making facilitating decisions activity domestic economy and transactions between organizer economy, as well imply equality, poverty, and quality life.
- b. Political Governance, covers the manufacturing process decision for the formulation of policy state politics.
- c. Administrative Governance, in the form of system implementation clothe icy.

2. Element of Good Governance

Development capacity and achievement of good governance are instruments main for resolving the various problem faced by the Indonesian nation when this. Challenge for all Public mature this is how to realize capable governance system realize realization prosperity everyone along anticipates impact negative from deed suspected corruption intense involve amount state officials, both at the center nor area.

The urgency for realizing good governance not only looked at suitable for resolve poverty and inequality but also very relevant with needs for the recovery process, stable economy and crisis politics that is getting worse as well as low performance and service public. That's why, in the implementation of government good governance no one could walk alone, but must involve various parties, ok Public nor circles private.

Opinion the in line with the view Taschereau and Compos (UNDP, 1997) also stated that "Good governance " is something that guarantees conditions there is a process of alignment, similarity, cohesion, and balance role, as well as the existence of each other control what is done by three components, namely Government, Civil Society, and Business".

So three-element terms (Government, Private Sector, and Civil Society) became component perpetrators within the country, to create something synergy that made something well-being in society. Country works create environment politics and conducive law, sector private push creation field work and income society, while Public alone accommodate interaction social politics and participate in various activity economic, social and political. That's why Miftah Thoha (2000) outlines bottom that the principle of democracy inherent in

good governance puts urgency for put power in the hands of people not in the hand ruler. Then, no there is fear for entering something gathering or union by needs heart conscience, and finally, respect for the moral difference opinion.

In line with thoughts, Riyaas Rasid and Mostopadidjaja (2002) put apparatus government as end spear implementation of clean good governance from KKN it seems also need to be investigated until how far is the danger deed collusion, corruption, and nepotism for life nation and state. It is essential for studied remember deeds it's very inherent with behavior apparatus alone. So with the view above, UNDP (1996) suggests three element main (domains) that need to be involved in the maintenance of good governance, namely the state, the private sector, and civil society organizations.

By functional Duty the most crucial country in the future come is how to realize a prosperous society, through enhancement of performance bureaucracy governance, and improvement of quality service public. Besides that, the state must be capable realize the development of sustainable humans while to do setting repeat to various supporting sectors to develop quality sources, and power for humans. Diverse the sectors in question, among others; sectors economic, political, social, cultural, legal, defense, infrastructure, strengthening democracy, decentralization, and others.

The government (country) has a very strategic position and role in to do structuring and integrating various sectors as described above, apart from that, the government must also be capable strive protecting to problem environment from the problem environment, which is still neglected. In the context of implementing good governance, sector private clear have a vast and strategic role, because, without the existence of involvement party confidential, I guess difficult for the government even no possible for could doing draft good governance optimally. One role important sector private in support realization of the concept of good governance is involvement in sector economy, of course, maximum no elements sectors staters, such as environment life, sector social, cultural and others. However, approaching the economy seems to be one of the critical pillars for the government (State) in push development economy nation, good concerning investment, marketing, and production so that in the end expected capable push development economy by national.

Like case state and private sector organization society (civil society organizations) also seems to be no can look at the adjacent eye in support of the realization of good governance. by functional, organizational culture play a role in facilitating interaction social, political, economic, legal, environmental life nor sector other. Besides that, corporate society also plays a role in doing checks and balances to authority and power of government (country) in operating his job as well as activity sector-related private with problem interest public. Other roles that the organization society can also play in implementing good governance is channel participation Public related with activity social, economic, political, legal, environmental life, and employment. In essence, organizational society can also contribute to contributing thought and emphasis to influencing policies that the government will issue. Thus, good governance enables system mechanism maintenance efficient and effective state government with constructive synergy between government, sector private sector, and community.

3. Principles Principles of Good & Clean Governance

In *Good and Clean Governance*, there are necessary principles to note, namely:

- a. Participation: Basic Participation is from opt-in inhabitant Public in making good decisions by direct nor past institution representative legitimately representing aspirations them. Form participation thorough this built based on the principle of democracy, that is, freedom to gather and reveal opinion constructive.
- b. Enforcement: Principles must manage government professionally and be supported by enforcement of authoritative law. The realization of excellent and clean government must also be balanced with a commitment to the government for enforcing the law that contains elements following:
 - 1) Rule of Law: every action elements state power and opportunity participation Public in life nation and state based on clear and firm laws and regulations, a guaranteed implementation by Correct as well as independent.
 - 2) Certainty: every life nation and state is governed by clear and definite laws, no duplicative and not contrary ones.
 - 3) Responsive law: rules set based on aspirations Public broad and capable of providing various public needs somewhat.

- 4) Enforcement of consistent and non - discriminatory laws.
- 5) Independence Judiciary: that is an independent judiciary, free from influence, power, or strength of others.
- c. Transparency: Principle is another supporting element that realizes excellent and clean governance. According to experts, if no there is principle this, can cause action corruption. Eight elements must be applied transparency: determination position/position/position, wealth office public giving the award determination policy health morality officials and apparatus service society security and order and approach strategic for enlightenment life society.
- d. Responsive: Basic responsive is in implementation government must respond to problems society must understand the needs community, must proactive study and analyze the needs of the community.
- e. Consensus: Principles consensus is that decision just conducted the deliberation process through consensus. How to take decision consensus have strength compel everyone involved for deciding it and decide all or part parties as well as tie part significant deliberative components. _
- f. Equality: principle equality is a similarity in treatment and service public. The principle this requires every implementation government to behave reasonably in Thing service public without differentiating ethnicity type belief gender and class society.
- g. Effectiveness and Efficiency: Good and clean governance must Fulfill criteria for practical (robust functional) and efficient (successful) use). Energy could be measured by how many big products can reach the interested Public from various groups. Efficiency generally is reckoned with rationality cost development to Fulfill the needs of all society.
- h. Accountability: Principle accountability is public accountability to the society that gave him authority to take care of his interests. Every office public sued for an account for answer all policies actions morals, and neutrality her attitude to society.
- i. Vision Strategic: Vision strategy is viewed strategy for facing the future come. Qualification Becomes important in the skeleton realization of good and clean governance. In other words, policy whatever will taken moment this must be taken into account as a result for ten or two twenty years to front.

4. Good and Clean Governance and Social Control

To realize good and clean government based on principles of good and clean governance at least could be conducted through program priorities :

- a. Strengthening function and role institution representative,
- b. independence institution judicial
- c. Professionalism and integrity apparatus government,
- d. Strengthening participation Public of civilian
- e. Enhancement of well-being of people in framework autonomy area.

With the implementation of the autonomy area, achievement level well-being could be realized by more rights, which in the end, will push for an independent society.

5. Good and Clean Governance and the Anti-Corruption Movement

Corruption is a problem big destructive success development national. Corruption acts in-demand individuals who use authority and position To use reach profit personal, detrimental interests general and country-specific. Corruption causes the economy Becomes unstable, politics that is not healthy, and the nation's moral decline that continues continuously slumped.

Jeremy Pope suggests that corruption occurs if opportunity and desire are at in same time. O the opportunity could be reduced with method stage change by systematic. Whereas desire could be reduced with the method reverse " profit " strategy high, risk low " to " profit low, risk height " with method enforce the law and scare by effective, and enforce mechanism accountability. Countermeasures of corruption could conduct with methods as follows :

- a. A There is political will and political action from state officials and leaders institution government in

- every unit work organization for To do step proactive prevention and eradication action corruption.
- b. Enforcement law by the firm and heavy (e.g. execution dead for criminals).
 - c. Build supporting institutions' efforts to eradicate corruption.
 - d. Build a mechanism organizing government that guarantees implementation of good and clean governance practices
 - e. Give anti-corruption education, good from formal or informal education.
 - f. corruption religious movement that movement builds awareness of religion and develops anti corruption spirituality.

6. Good and Clean Governance and Bureaucratic Performance Public Service

Service general or service public is gift service both by the government, parties private on name government or party private to the community, with or without payment To use Fulfill needs and/ or interest society. Several reasons why the service public Becomes point strategic for starting the development and implementation of *Good and Clean Governance* in Indonesia.

To realize the implementation of *good governance* by consistent and *sustainable* job, especially the good governance directed at efforts create ion clean and authoritative apparatus. For that rank bureaucracy government must understand the sencofo bureaucracy that alone tied with the creation of good governance in question. In context David Obsorn and Gaebler (1992) present 10 concofepts bureaucracy as follows:

- a. *Catalytic Government: Steering rather than rowing.* Apparatus and bureaucracy play a role as catalyst, which is not must doing alone development but enough control resources in the community .With thereby apparatus and bureaucracy must capable optimizing use of funds and resources in accordance with interest public.
- b. *Community-owned government: empower communities to solve their own problems, rather than marrely deliver service.* Apparatus and bureaucracy must empower Public in gift in the service. Organizations society like cooperatives, NGOs and so on, it is necessary invited for solve the problem alone, like problem safety, cleanliness, necessities schools, settlements cheap and so on.
- c. *Competitive government: promote and encourage competition, rather than monopolies.* Apparatus and bureaucracy must create competition in every service. With existence competition so sector effort private and government competitive and forced work by more professional and efficient.
- d. *Mission-driven government: be driven by mission rather than rules*". Apparatus and bureaucracy must To do activities that emphasize to achievement what constitutes its "mission" rather than emphasizing rules .Every organization given leeway for produce something in accordance with his mission .
- e. *Result-oriented government: result oriented by funding outcomes rather than inputs.* Apparatus and bureaucracy should oriented to good performance. Such an agency must given more opportunities big compared to institutions whose performance less.
- f. *Customer-driver government: meet the needs of the customer rather than the bureaucracy.* Apparatus and bureaucracy must prioritize fulfillment needs society no needs herself alone .
- g. *The pricing government: concretrate on earning money rather than just speeding it.* apparatus bureaucracy must have officers who know the right way with make money for the organization , beside smart save cost . With so the employees will used to life thrifty .
- h. *Anticipatory government: invest in preventing problems rather than curing crises.* Anticipatory apparatus and bureaucracy .More good prevent than extinguishing fire. More good prevent epidemic than treat disease. With thereby will there is a "mental switch" in apparatus area .
- i. *Decentralized government: decentralized authority rahter than build hierarchy.* Required decentralization in management government, from oriented hierarchy Becomes participatory with development cooperation team. With thereby organization subordinate will more free for be creative and take necessary initiative. _
- j. *Market-oriented government: solve problems by influencing market forces rather than by treating public programs.* Apparatus and bureaucracy must notice market power . supply based on need or market demand and not on the contrary . For that policy must based on market needs.

7. Good Governance in National Defense Human Capital Development

Development career, or development in general, can be interpreted as an effort to change or increase the career of an employee from different positions in different spaces and groups. Clutter and Susan (2003:107) argue that a development career is an activity source of power for human resources (HR) who help employees plan future careers to develop their abilities. This Thingthing is supported by opportunity development compatible career with a growth company (Ruky, 2014).

Accountability, together with transparency, is one of the principles most important in implementing good governance (Nubatonis, 2014). Accountability means that the taker's decision government, sector private sector and organizations Public other must responsible answer good to Public nor interested institutions. The format of the report is highly dependent on the format of each organization. As moving agencies further going to professionalism, TNI, of course, does not miss from demands for the operating organization by the responsible answer. In line with system accountability implemented by the President Republic of Indonesia to the whole institution national, including TNI, the development of a career in the TNI environment must be based on the related principles of good governance accountability.

To reach Thingthing above and implement the main mission military is precise, efficient, effective, and quality. Of course, need existence professional components, responsible answers, and fairness and sincerity. Competent in every field. Pamen TNI must depend on qualified skills and competencies for operating tasks (Uar, 2016). Application principle the in construction career TNI soldiers, in the end, will create justice for every individual soldier. one component of accountability that is an organization must be capable take responsibility for all things that have been done.

III. CONCLUSION

The conclusion is good governance is how to serve the public with the best to society. If the service is efficient, meaning reverse comparison between input and output achieved with minimal input, then level efficiency becomes better. Service input could be money, energy, time, and materials used to reach the output. Service prices public must be affordable by ability economy society. Second, nonparticipating services. It means system service that applies user waiter by fair without differentiating and based on social status economy, ethnicity, party religion, the background behind usage service no can made consideration in giving service.

The government needs serious handle management source power nationally by sustainable involving the whole component nation and putting forward the interest of nations and countries above the interest of individuals and groups. Integration pattern development national Among aspects of national defense and welfare society, good level policy and operational must quickly realize state sovereignty that is integrated, substantial, and significant in the future. Good governance in building threat-based defense and security and maximizing the potential capabilities of the Indonesian state.

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